

CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. Curriculum development is an essentially practical activity to improve the quality of language teaching through the use of systematic planning, development, and review practices in all aspects of a language program. In this article I will write about the importance, the stages of developing curriculum, how it is organized and the components of English language curriculum. Moreover, I will give some samples from the works of well-known experts in developing curriculum in teaching English language

Keywords: curriculum, components, stages, quality, systematic planning, practical activity, review practises.

РАЗРАБОТКА ПРОГРАММЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. Разработка учебного плана — это, по сути, практическая деятельность по повышению качества преподавания языка за счет использования практики систематического планирования, разработки и пересмотра всех аспектов языковой программы. В этой статье я напишу о важности, этапах разработки учебного плана, как он организован и составные части учебного плана по английскому языку. Кроме того, я приведу некоторые образцы из работ известных специалистов по разработке учебных планов по обучению английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: учебный план, компоненты, этапы, качество, системное планирование, практическая деятельность, обзорные практики.

Curriculum development is an essentially practical activity to improve the quality of language teaching through the use of systematic planning, development, and review practices in all aspects of a language program. Beyond creating shared goals between teachers and students, curriculum also standardizes the learning goals for an entire school and provides a clear path for students to progress from one grade to another.

5 stages of curriculum development

The curriculum development process can be categorized into five basic steps: 1) needs assessment, 2) the planning session, 3) content development, 4) pilot delivery and revision, and 5) the completed curriculum package. The ideal situation is to have, at a minimum, 12 - 18 months to design and develop a curriculum. If teachers follow these 5 stages that will be easier to develop curriculum while they are teaching English language.

1. Needs assessment stage

The needs assessment and analysis step in curriculum development systematically focuses on learning about an issue or problem and the people who are directly effected by it. A needs assessment provides the information to determine outcomes (educational objectives) based on a factual foundation and learners needs.

2. The planning session stage

The Planning Session and Content Development steps typically occur in tandem. It is during the planning session that discussions occur about the content that is to be developed and delivered in the curriculum. The team actively participates in the design and development of the curriculum.

3. Content development stage

Content development -- the ability to select, sequence and implement instructional tasks to meet a specific instructional outcome -- is a critical skill for physical education teachers

4. Pilot delivery and revision stage.

This is the stage at which the planned curriculum is introduced into the schools and colleges. It is the stage in which the newly developed and tried curriculum is made publicly available. This is the logical process to undertake after the tryout of the curriculum.

5. Completed package stage

The final element in an evaluation strategy is "delivering the pay off (i.e., getting the results into the hands of people who can use them). In this step, suggestions for what and how to report to key shareholders, especially funding and policy decision makers, are provided and a brief discussion on how to secure resources

One way to achieve learning is through the interaction of the teaching and learning process. Teaching and learning interactions contain meaning that the teaching and learning activities of teachers and students in this interaction will influence each other, meaning students do not learn from their teachers but teachers will also learn a lot from these activities carrying out teaching assignments at certain institutions. Teaching and learning interactions can occur within institutions, whether in the form of schools, households, or social institutions. That known as formal, and informal. Schools are institutions that are formally responsible for the sustainability of the education process. Education that informal education institutions are education directed at specific goals. To be able to realize these goals, the curriculum is a tool that brings all educational activities to the desired goals. The curriculum is a "guideline" in determining the goals and direction of education in the future. With the curriculum, the education process will run in a clear direction. In the curriculum process, education will be a reference that must be used as a guide, both by managers and by education providers. The curriculum is occupying a very important position in education, because it is related to components, content, goals, methods, processes, to education evaluation which in turn will determine the types and qualifications of graduates. According to Wolfgang Klein, (Melbourne: Cambridge University Press, 1990), The meaning of foreign language is different from the second language. The difference is on the usage. If the language mentioned has a communicative function in a certain society or used in daily activities, for instance, in the Javanese society, the language is called a second language. But if the language has no certain function in daily communication in society, for instance, English and Mandarin in Indonesia, the language is considered as a foreign language. Language learning means acquiring the ability to ask and answer questions, to make statements, and to produce the normal authentic, forms used by native English speakers.

Conclusion

Curriculum development is a complex process that requires commitment of the organization responsible and the various stakeholders. The process should be conducted with transparency and systematically so that the outcomes of the whole process become credible.

REFERENCES

1. Departemen Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan RI tentang Petunjuk Pembinaan pendidikan di sekolah. Jakarta 1994
2. Undang – undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 tentang National Education System. Jakarta 2003.
3. Mas Nihayatul Amal Rawamerta. 2013. English Learning In Indonesia. Jawa Barat: SDN SUKAMERTA
4. Idi, Abdullah. 2011 Pengembangan Kurikulum; Teori dan Praktik. Yogyakarta: Arruz 2011.
5. Klein, Wolfgang. 1990 Second Language Acquisition, Melbourne: Cambridge University Press, 1990. K. E. Suyanto, Kasih